

Parvulastra exigua

Dwarf cushion star

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

Group: Echinoderm

Size: 20 mm

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Distribution:

This species is distributed along the South African coast from the west coast to KwaZulu-Natal.

Importance:

The dwarf cushion star is a widespread and ecologically significant intertidal species in South Africa. It contributes to biodiversity by maintaining balance in rocky shore ecosystems and serving as prey and grazer. Sequencing its genome will provide insights into adaptation to harsh intertidal conditions, population connectivity, and resilience to environmental change, supporting conservation and enhancing understanding of echinoderm evolution within South Africa's unique marine biodiversity.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 61.29 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 2.34 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.33 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.0% [Single: 94.1%, Duplicated: 3.9%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 110 kilobases

Contig number: 17 444

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